

1 **Number of words text:** 4107 words
2 **Number of words abstract:** 249 words.
3 **Number of tables:** 3
4 **Number of figures:** 3
5 **Number of references:** 52
6 **Number of supplementary tables:** 5
7 **Number of supplementary texts, code and figures:** 5
8

9 **Development and Validation of a Prognostic Model and Risk Calculator for the**
10 **Estimation of Bipolar-spectrum disorders Risk in Hospitalised Adolescents with**
11 **Non-psychotic/non-bipolar Mental Disorders**

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78 **Funding:** In part supported by a grant from the John and Maxine Bendheim Foundation
79 (Fellowship Award for Research to CU Correll).

80 **Conflict of interest:** Dr Salazar de Pablo has received honoraria from Janssen Cilag, Lundbeck,
81 Angelini and Menarini. Dr Radua has received CME honoraria from Inspira Networks for a
82 machine learning course promoted by Adamed, outside the submitted work. Prof. Arango was
83 supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII),
84 co-financed by the European Union, ERDF Funds from the European Commission, “A way of
85 making Europe”, financed by the European Union - NextGenerationEU
86 (PMP21/00051), PI19/01024. PI22/01824 CIBERSAM, Madrid Regional Government
87 (B2017/BMD-3740 AGES-CM-2), European Union Structural Funds, European Union Seventh
88 Framework Program, European Union H2020 Program under the Innovative Medicines Initiative
89 2 Joint Undertaking: Project PRISM-2 (Grant agreement No.101034377), Project AIMS-2-TRIALS

90 (Grant agreement No 777394), Horizon Europe, the National Institute of Mental Health of the
91 National Institutes of Health under Award Number 1U01MH124639-01 (Project ProNET) and
92 Award Number 5P50MH115846-03 (project FEP-CAUSAL), Fundación Familia Alonso, and
93 Fundación Alicia Koplowitz. Dr Solmi received honoraria/has been a consultant for Angelini,
94 AbbVie, Boehringer Ingelheim, Lundbeck, Otsuka. Dr. Guinart has been a consultant and/or
95 advisor or has received honoraria from: Angelini, Otsuka, Lundbeck and Teva. Prof Correll has
96 been a consultant and/or advisor to or has received honoraria from: AbbVie, Acadia, Adock
97 Ingram, Alkermes, Allergan, Angelini, Aristo, Biogen, Boehringer-Ingelheim, Bristol-Meyers
98 Squibb, Cardio Diagnostics, Cerevel, CNX Therapeutics, Compass Pathways, Darnitsa, Delpor,
99 Denovo, Eli Lilly, Gedeon Richter, Hikma, Holmusk, IntraCellular Therapies, Jamjoom Pharma,
100 Janssen/J&J, Karuna, LB Pharma, Lundbeck, MedAvante-ProPhase, MedInCell, Merck, Mindpax,
101 Mitsubishi Tanabe Pharma, Mylan, Neurocrine, Neurelis, Newron, Noven, Novo Nordisk, Otsuka,
102 Pharmabrain, PPD Biotech, Recordati, Relmada, Reviva, Rovi, Sage, Sanofi, Seqirus, SK Life
103 Science, Sumitomo Pharma America, Sunovion, Sun Pharma, Supernus, Tabuk, Takeda, Teva,
104 Tolmar, Vertex, Viatris and Xenon. He provided expert testimony for Janssen and Otsuka. He
105 served on a Data Safety Monitoring Board for Compass Pathways, Denovo, Lundbeck, Relmada,
106 Reviva, Rovi, Supernus, and Teva. He has received grant support from Janssen and Takeda. He
107 received royalties from UpToDate and is also a stock option holder of Cardio Diagnostics, Kuleon
108 Biosciences, LB Pharma, Mindpax, Quantic and Terran.

109 **Acknowledgments:** None.

110

111

112 **ABSTRACT**

113 We aimed to develop and validate a risk estimation model for developing bipolar-spectrum
114 disorders (BSD) in psychiatrically hospitalized adolescents based on clinical characteristics,
115 including putatively prodromal symptoms. Adolescent inpatients (ages=12-18 years) with non-
116 psychotic/non-BSD diagnoses were recruited for the Adolescent Mood Disorder and Psychosis
117 Study (AMDPS), a longitudinal, prospective 5-year follow-up cohort. We assessed prevalence
118 and severity of syndromal/subsyndromal psychopathology at baseline using the validated
119 Bipolar Prodrome Symptom Interview and Scale–Prospective. We carried out machine learning
120 analyses (Lasso-Cox regression analyses, LCR) to create a calculator to estimate the risk of
121 developing BSD based on baseline demographic/comorbidity/illness/treatment characteristics.
122 Of 105 adolescents (age=15.6±1.3 years, females=72.4%), we observed that 18 developed BSD.
123 The cumulated estimated risk of BSD was 5%/22%/29%/36% at 1/2/3/4 years. BSD development
124 was associated with presence of persistent depressive disorder (HR=4.0, p<0.018) at baseline,
125 treatment with mood stabilizers (hazard ratio (HR)=3.9, p=0.006), and ADHD medications
126 (HR=3.3, p=0.023). BSD development risk estimation calculator included the prevalence of
127 inflated self-esteem/grandiosity ($\beta=0.83$) and racing thoughts ($\beta=0.08$) and the severity of
128 overtalkativeness ($\beta=0.03$) and increased energy ($\beta=0.04$). For predicting BSD onset within the
129 first 20 months, the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) indicated
130 acceptable to strong discrimination (cross-validation AUC=0.72; bootstrap out-of-bag validation
131 AUC=0.86). Codes used in this study are provided in the R package “easy.glmnet”. In conclusion,
132 in this prognostic model/calculator, presence and severity of subthreshold (hypo)mania-like
133 symptoms conferred increased risk of BSD development in youth, informing preventive efforts
134 to identify individuals at risk for BSD and improve their outcomes.

135 **Key Words:** bipolar disorder, adolescents, clinical risk.

136

137 **INTRODUCTION**

138 Bipolar disorder (BD) is a severe mental illness characterized by fluctuations in mood and energy
139 ¹. BD is associated with significant impairments in cognitive, social, and everyday functioning ².
140 BD affects >1% of the world's population and ranks second regarding the greatest effect on days
141 out of role functioning ³. BD contributes to 9.9 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYS) ⁴.
142 Furthermore, individuals with BD have reduced life expectancy of up to 20 years, particularly
143 due to suicide (accounting for 15% of deaths) and cardiovascular disease (accounting for 35-40%
144 of deaths) ⁵. However, there is a diagnostic delay of 5–10 years and significant duration of
145 untreated illness ⁶, preventing prompt efforts to ameliorate poor outcomes.

146 Early signs and symptoms before full-blown mania have been described ⁷. Such subthreshold
147 symptoms preceding BD include disturbances in mood, circadian rhythms and behaviour ⁸, with
148 a meta-analytically calculated duration of 27.1±23.1 months ⁷. While the presence of a clearly
149 defined mania prodrome remains debated ⁹, rating scales and checklists, such as the Bipolar
150 Prodrome Symptom Interview and Scale-Full Prospective (BPSS-FP) ¹⁰, Early Phase Inventory for
151 Bipolar Disorders (EPIbipolar) ¹¹, or the Semistructured Interview for Bipolar At Risk States
152 (SIBARS) ¹² have been developed to measure initial symptoms and define a bipolar risk
153 syndrome. BD is associated with a wide range of risk factors, including family history of BD ^{13,14},
154 obstetric complications ¹⁵, adverse life events ¹⁶, anxiety and sleep problems ¹⁷. Moreover,
155 specific symptoms of mania and depression ¹⁰ are associated with a development of bipolar
156 spectrum disorders (BSD, i.e., (BD-I, BD-II and BD-not otherwise specified (NOS)), ranging
157 between 7.1% and 23.4% at 2 year follow-up ¹⁸. According to an electronic health care data
158 study, treatment setting is also related to risk of psychosis/BD, which by age 28 years was 1.8%
159 for individuals without any child and adolescent mental health services (CAMHS) contact during
160 childhood or adolescence, being 12.8% for those with prior outpatient CAMHS contact, and
161 24.0% for those with prior inpatient CAMHS admission ¹⁹. Other studies have evaluated the BD

162 prodrome retrospectively ^{7, 20}. However, very few studies comprehensively characterized and
163 evaluated putative prodromal symptoms of (future) BSD, using a validated instrument ²¹.

164 The field of precision psychiatry and the number of prediction modelling studies has multiplied
165 in recent years ²². However, most focused on diagnostic models and other mental health
166 conditions, including psychosis or ADHD ²³. One risk calculator developed for individuals with
167 familial high-risk for BD found that dimensional measures of mania, depression, anxiety, and
168 mood lability; psychosocial functioning; and parental age at mood disorder predicted the
169 individual risk of developing BSD ²⁴. A second risk calculator from a 22-year birth cohort found
170 that suicide risk, generalized anxiety disorder, parental physical abuse, and financial problems
171 were associated with BD ²⁵. Another study found that the best-fit model for predicting BD was a
172 progressive sequence from nonspecific childhood antecedents to adolescent depression to
173 index manic or hypomanic episode ²⁶.

174 To our knowledge, no risk estimation model or calculator has been developed to evaluate the
175 development of BSD in psychiatrically hospitalized adolescents. We aimed to prospectively
176 evaluate the presence, severity and frequency of risk symptoms (including manic, depressive
177 and general symptoms) plus their predictive value for future development of BSD.

178 Specifically, we aimed to a) evaluate the risk of adolescents initially hospitalized for the
179 treatment of mood, anxiety and behavioral disorders but without psychotic disorder/ BSD
180 diagnoses during follow-up, and b) use machine learning techniques to develop and validate a
181 risk estimation calculator for the development of BSD in initially hospitalized adolescents. We
182 hypothesized that (1) a significant proportion of adolescents requiring inpatient treatment for
183 non-psychotic/non-BSD conditions would develop BSD, and (2) presence and severity of some
184 subthreshold mania-like symptoms would predict who has a higher risk of developing BSD.

185 **METHODS**

186 **Design and setting**

187 The Adolescent Mood Disorder and Psychosis Study (AMDPS) ²⁷ study is a longitudinal,
188 prospective 5-year follow-up cohort study. Participants were recruited between 09/2009 and
189 07/2017 from the child and adolescent inpatient unit of Zucker Hillside Hospital. Zucker Hillside
190 Hospital is a semi-urban, tertiary care facility for populations in Brooklyn and Queens in New
191 York, as well as from more middle class and affluent regions on Long Island. After recruitment,
192 participants were invited for follow-up interviews, typically on a yearly basis, until 01/2020.
193 AMDPS was registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT01383915). This was a STROBE-compliant ²⁸
194 study (details available in eTable 1) reporting on a TRIPOD-compliant prediction model (details
195 available in eTables 2-3) ^{29, 30}.

196 The protocol, procedures, consent and assent documents were approved by the Northwell
197 Health System Ethics Committee in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975 and
198 UNESCO Universal Declaration on human rights. Written informed consent was obtained from
199 all subject's legal representatives/guardians and written assent was obtained from adolescents,
200 obtaining informed consent if turning 18 years old during follow-up.

201 **Participants**

202 Inclusion criteria for the overall AMDPS study were: (1) age 12–18 years; (2) hospitalized at the
203 adolescent inpatient unit of Zucker Hillside Hospital, Glen Oaks, NY; (3) admission chart
204 diagnosis of any affective or psychotic disorder, (4) subject and legal guardian (if subject<18)
205 willing and able to provide written, informed consent/assent. Exclusion criteria were: (1) an
206 estimated IQ<70 as per Wide Range Achievement Test III Reading; (2) DSM-5 clinical criteria for
207 autism-spectrum disorders or pervasive developmental disorder (chart diagnoses), and (3)
208 history of any neurological or medical condition known to affect the brain. For the purpose of
209 this present study, which includes adolescents with non-psychotic/non-bipolar mental disorders
210 only, we excluded further (1) participants without complete BPSS-FP information (e.g. aborted
211 interview); (2) participants with any DSM-5 research diagnosis of a psychotic disorder (DSM-5

212 295) or a non-psychotic BSD (296.40-89) (see diagnostic tools below), and (3) participants
213 without follow-up assessments in whom BSD development could not be assessed.

214

215 **Diagnostic assessments**

216 Psychiatric diagnoses were established via the Schedule for Affective Disorders and
217 Schizophrenia for School-Age Children-Present and Lifetime version (K-SADS-PL) and the
218 Structured Clinical Interview for DSM Disorders (SCID) comprising the Childhood Disorders
219 Version of the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM Disorders (KID-SCID) augmented for
220 depressive disorders and BSD designations by the BPSS-FP (see below and eText 1 for Bipolar
221 Spectrum Disorders characterizations), conducted separately with patients and caregivers
222 according to DSM-5 criteria. BSD designations included BD-I defined by the occurrence of ≥ 1
223 manic episode; BD-II defined by the occurrence of ≥ 1 hypomanic episode and ≥ 1 depressive
224 episode, and BD-NOS defined by symptoms of BD and a change in functioning, but lacking
225 sufficient duration or severity for a BD-I or BD-II diagnosis³¹, using for BD-NOS specifically the
226 definition from the Course and Outcome of Bipolar Youth (COBY) study, i.e., a distinct period of
227 abnormally elevated, expansive, or irritable mood plus either ≥ 2 DSM-5 manic symptoms (≥ 3 if
228 the mood was irritability only) that were clearly associated with the onset of abnormal mood
229 plus a clear change in functioning; and presence of the elated and/or irritable mood and
230 (hypo)manic symptoms for ≥ 4 cumulative hours and ≥ 4 cumulative days. Final diagnoses were
231 determined in diagnostic consensus conferences reviewing clinical and rating scale information
232 with the principal investigator (CUC), a board-certified child and adolescent psychiatrist with
233 ample experience in the diagnosis of BSD. Assessments based on the patient and based on the
234 caregiver interview were integrated counting the higher severity/frequency symptom (assuming
235 that symptoms are more likely forgotten than invented or exaggerated). Baseline interviews
236 were typically conducted a few days after hospitalization, while follow-up interviews were
237 scheduled annually. To conduct AMDPS diagnostic and clinical assessments, experienced

238 clinicians had to be certified by the study principal investigator (CUC) after having gone through
239 a structured training program.

240

241 **Clinical assessments**

242 The BPSS-FP¹⁰ is a semi-structured interview that was developed to detect prodromal and
243 subsyndromal bipolar states and to assess the evolution of BSD. Full details on the BPSS_FP are
244 provided in eText 2. Briefly, other scales were administered to caregivers and youth including
245 the Clinical Global Impression – Severity scale (CGI-S), which assessed the overall severity of
246 illness, the Global Assessment of Functioning scale (GAF), which assessed the level on
247 functionality, as well as The Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS) and the
248 Young Mania Rating Scale (YMRS) which were used to assess affective symptoms.

249

250 **Data analysis**

251 We used univariate Cox regression analyses (i.e., survival analysis) to assess the effects of the
252 baseline characteristics on the risk of BSD development considering dropouts. We analyzed each
253 variable separately.

254 We also carried out machine learning analyses to create a calculator that estimates the risk of
255 development of BSD. We introduced into the model the severity and frequency of BPSS-FP items
256 (Table 2), as well as the demographic, comorbidities, illness and treatment characteristics
257 detailed in Table 1. We used Lasso Cox regression analyses (LCR). Relevance of a predictor within
258 the model was defined as the absolute value of its standardized coefficient divided by the sum
259 of the absolute values of all standardized coefficients³². To avoid over-fitting, we used two
260 strategies: a) a leave-one-out cross-validation, in which the cohort was iteratively divided into a
261 training and a test sample, and b) a bootstrap out-of-bag validation, in which bootstrap samples
262 were used for training while out-of-bag samples (i.e., individuals not selected in the bootstrap

263 sample in that replication) were used for validation. In the training sample, we fitted and applied
264 Gaussian/binomial lasso regressions to impute the missing continuous/binary predictors
265 multiple times. Then, we fitted a Cox lasso regression analysis to create a prediction model (one
266 per imputation dataset). Afterwards, in the test sample, we applied the Gaussian/binomial lasso
267 regression analyses to input the missing predictors, and we applied the Cox lasso regressions to
268 predict the development of BSD (averaged across imputations). At the end of the leave-one-out
269 cross-validation, we had estimated one BSD development risk profile for each patient of the
270 cohort, but we never used the same patients to create and validate the model. Similarly, after
271 1000 bootstrap replications, we had repeatedly estimated BSD development risk profile for each
272 patient of the cohort but never used the same patients to create and validate the model. The
273 reason for using two different strategies is that accuracy estimates from cross-validation may
274 be less reliable than those from external dataset validation. Still, in simulations, we found that
275 this problem might be mitigated in some scenarios when using bootstrap with out-of-bag
276 validation (see eCode 1).

277 We then calculated the area under the curve (AUC) over time. AUC expresses the ability to
278 separate individuals with and without a certain outcome and expresses how well the model
279 ranks patients by BSD risk. This discriminative validity is considered 'acceptable' when AUC
280 scores are between 0.7–0.8, 'good' between 0.8–0.9, and 'excellent' when >0.9 ³³. Finally, we
281 split the sample into two groups (low-risk and high-risk) based on the estimated risk threshold
282 associated with the lowest Akaike information criteria (AIC). Significance level was set at
283 $\alpha=0.05$, and all tests were two-tailed. We provide the codes used in this study in the R
284 package "easy.glmnet".

285

286 **RESULTS**

287 **Patient flow**

288 Altogether, 403 adolescents consented to participate in the AMDPS. Of these, 324 subjects had
289 complete information at baseline. Seventy-six patients had a KID-SCID-verified psychotic
290 disorder at baseline, and 51 had a non-psychotic BSD disorder. Of the 197 participants eligible
291 for the study, 105 participants had follow-up information and were included in the study (Figure
292 1). A comparison of sociodemographic characteristics (age, sex, race), comorbidity (depressive
293 disorders, trauma- and stressor-related disorders, personality disorder traits, anxiety disorders,
294 disruptive behavior disorders or substance use disorders) and pharmacological treatment (% on
295 antipsychotics, antidepressants, mood stabilizers, anxiolytics or ADHD medications) did not
296 reveal statistically significant or clinically meaningful differences between youths with vs.
297 without those for whom follow- up data (all $p>0.05$) (comparison provided in eTable 4).

298 **Demographic, comorbidities, illness and treatment characteristics**

299 The 105 adolescents with follow-up data were on average 15.4 ± 1.3 years old, 72.4% were
300 females and 54.5% were White (Table1). Altogether, patients had 3.2 ± 1.8 psychiatric diagnoses,
301 including depressive disorders (81.9%), anxiety disorders (44.8%), disruptive behavior disorders
302 (41.0%), personality disorder traits (18.1%), trauma- and stressor-related disorders (14.3%), and
303 substance use disorders (12.4%) (Table 1). Patients were on average moderately to severely ill
304 (CGI-S= 4.2 ± 1.0) and 97.1% received at least one psychotropic medication at baseline
305 (mean= 2.7 ± 1.7) (antipsychotics=61.9%, antidepressants=60.0%, mood stabilizers=36.2%,
306 anxiolytics=22.9%, and anti-ADHD medications=12.4%) (Table 1).

307 **Demographic, comorbidities, illness, and treatment characteristics associated with BSD** 308 **development**

309 Of the 105 participants with prospective data, 18 developed new-onset BSD, of which 9
310 developed BD-NOS, 1 BD-II, and 8 BD-I (5 without psychotic features and 3 with). As per the
311 Kaplan-Meier estimator, which considers loss to follow-up, the cumulated estimated BSD risk
312 was 5% at 1 year, 22% at 2 years, 29% at 3 years, and 36% at 4 years (Figure 2).

313 BSD development was associated with the presence of persistent depressive disorder (HR=4.0,
314 $p<0.018$), more baseline mood stabilizers (hazard ratio (HR)=3.9, $p=0.006$), including lithium
315 (HR=2.8, $p=0.03$), and baseline ADHD medications (HR=3.3, $p=0.023$). BSD development was also
316 associated with the severity of manic symptoms (HR=1.08, $p=0.009$). No associations were found
317 with demographic characteristics (age, sex, or race), other psychiatric diagnoses, other
318 psychopathology scores (MADRS, CGI-S), or baseline treatment with other
319 psychopharmacologic drug classes (all $p>0.05$) (see Table 2 and eTable 5 for details). See eFigure
320 1 for 2 Kaplan-Meier transition figures comparing the high- vs. low-risk group.

321 **Predictors of developing BSD, predictive value of BPSS-FP items, and risk calculator**

322 According to cross-validation, BSD development risk was predicted by the prevalence of inflated
323 self-esteem/grandiosity (M3, $\beta=0.83$), racing thoughts (M6, $\beta=0.08$), overtalkativeness (M5,
324 $\beta=0.03$), increased energy (M8, $\beta=0.04$) and mood lability (G1, $\beta=0.001$). Note the four
325 predictors with $\geq 5\%$ predicting relevance were 1) prevalence of self-esteem/grandiosity (68.1%),
326 2) severity of increased energy (8.2%), 3) severity of overtalkativeness (7.6%), and 4) prevalence
327 of racing thoughts (5.3%). The AUC was statistically significant for estimating the risk of
328 developing BSD during the first 17–23 months (Figure 3), when 11–13 patients had developed
329 BSD (AUC = 0.71, peaking at 0.72 in month 20, and decreasing to 0.70 in month 18 and to 0.69
330 in month 23, eFigure 2). Some AUCs were also statistically significant for estimating the risk
331 during the first 13 months, although these AUCs were based on only six transitions. Bootstrap
332 out-of-bag validation yielded the same predictors, plus a list of others (M1, M4, M10, D12, G5,
333 MADRS, several diagnoses – note however that this validation involved creating thousands of
334 models thus increasing the likelihood of adding other regressors). The AUC from the bootstrap
335 out-of-bag validation was slightly higher, reaching 0.85 for estimating the risk of developing BSD
336 during the first 20–22 months, and rising to 0.86 at month 22. Again, some AUCs were also

337 statistically significant for estimating the risk during the first 16 months, although these AUCs
338 were based on only nine transitions.

339 The following formula underlies the online calculator available at
340 <https://www.imardgroup.com/bsd-risk-calculator>, calculating where patients fall regarding the
341 high- vs. low-risk cutoff of 0.172. The formula is $0.833 * [\text{Prevalence of inflated self-}$
342 $\text{esteem/grandiosity}] + 0.079 * [\text{Prevalence of racing thoughts}] + 0.030 * [\text{Severity of}$
343 $\text{overtalkativeness}] + 0.035 * [\text{Severity of increased energy}]$. For descriptive purposes, we also
344 provide the probability of developing a BSD within the first 20 months, as estimated from a
345 logistic regression analysis (dependent variable: observed status at 20 months; independent
346 variable: logarithm of the estimated risk plus $\epsilon=1e-16$ – we added ϵ because risk might be zero).

347

348 **DISCUSSION**

349 We observed that around 17% of adolescents developed BSD at ≤ 5 -year follow-up, representing
350 an estimated LCR risk of 22% at two years and 36% at four years, when taking risk factors and
351 dropouts into account. Notably, at least in this sample, the first three years represented the
352 highest risk period for BSD development. In univariate analyses persistent depressive disorder,
353 and more treatment with mood stabilizers and ADHD medications (being vulnerable to
354 confounding by indication) well as subthreshold mania-like symptoms were associated with BSD
355 transition. Moreover, our BSD risk estimation model included baseline presence of inflated self-
356 esteem/grandiosity and racing thoughts, as well as baseline severity of overtalkativeness, and
357 increased energy. Presence/severity of these mania-like symptoms estimated BSD risk within
358 the first 17-22 months of follow-up with an AUC of 0.71-0.85.

359 A previous Finnish national register study found that in adolescents aged 13-17 years old, the
360 risk of developing BD 11-17 (mean=5.9) years later, by age 28 (measured through electronic
361 health care data), was 0.7% for individuals who had not attended CAMHS during childhood or

362 adolescence, 5.0% for those with a history of any CAMHS contact, and 7.9% for those with a
363 history of inpatient CAMHS admission¹⁹. Similarly, a recent study from Sweden of 114
364 adolescents and 114 adults from outpatient and inpatient settings reported a 7.0% development
365 rate to BD over three years in patients diagnosed with major depressive disorder (MDD)³⁴. In a
366 longitudinal study with 3.9 years of follow-up, BP-NOS was stable in 46.1% of patients, but 38.5%
367 transitioned to BP-I over time. Psychotic symptoms during prior depressive episodes (MDD)
368 increased the risk of transition to BP-I 11-fold. Each individual symptom of mania increased the
369 risk of transition to BP-I by 1.41³⁵. Notably, in that study, adolescents were significantly less
370 likely to transition to BD in the first three years than propensity-score balanced adults (odds
371 ratio=0.42; 95% CI=0.20-0.88; p=0.02), despite having more outpatient visits at baseline.
372 However, both groups experienced substantially reduced inpatient care following the BD
373 diagnosis, plus a marked decline in antidepressant use without increased lithium use³⁴. Although
374 our observed transition rate to BSD was higher (17.8%) than transition rates in these two studies
375 (7.9% in adolescents with prior inpatient care¹⁹ and 7.0% in adolescents with MDD³⁴, when
376 restricting our analyses to BD-I and BD-II, the rate of 8.6% is comparable, although the mean
377 follow-up of 1.5 years was shorter. However, in our study, adolescents and caregivers
378 underwent a detailed and lengthy diagnostic interview process with validated diagnostic
379 instruments by trained interviewers, which likely reduced the rate of underdiagnosis or late
380 diagnosis of BD, which is more likely in clinical care^{36, 37}.

381 Our machine learning analyses, and risk estimation model successfully estimated the BSD
382 transition risk during approximately the second year of follow-up with 0.71-0.85 accuracy.
383 Mania-like symptoms, i.e. inflated self-esteem/grandiosity, racing thoughts, overtalkativeness,
384 increased energy and mood lability were associated with increased risk of BSD. Symptoms of
385 (hypo)mania, even those with lower severity, have been associated with lower self-esteem,
386 poorer emotional states, poorer social acceptance, and lower overall quality of life³⁸. Relatedly,

387 in an adolescent inpatient sample, subthreshold mania-like symptoms also best differentiated
388 BD depression from unipolar depression³⁹. Other factors significantly associated with BD
389 development were early age of onset of major depressive disorder (4.8 years earlier than those
390 who without transition), and mood lability⁴⁰ among others.

391 Mood lability also seems to be associated with increased risk of development of BSD at follow-
392 up. Of note, the BPSS-FP⁴¹ screen for mania-like symptoms that map onto the BD-I and BD-II
393 criteria that may be suprathreshold or subthreshold, but also includes mood lability as a general
394 symptom item. The mood lability item is also included in the BPSS-Abbreviated-Prospicive
395 (BPSS-AP)⁴² and in the self-rating instrument (BPSS-Abbreviated Screen (BPSS-AS) for patients
396 and for informants⁴¹. Mood lability has previously been shown to predict the development of
397 BSD in individuals with subthreshold symptoms in a risk calculator which, unlike ours, included
398 socio-demographic factors and family history as their predictors⁴³, but which lacked detailed
399 ratings of attenuated or suprathreshold symptoms of mania and depression as provided by the
400 BPSS-FP. In offspring of individuals with BD, a history of anxiety disorders or disruptive behavior
401 disorders has been associated with elevated risk of BSD⁴⁴. However, while 72% of the bipolar
402 offspring developed a lifetime DSM-IV axis I disorder and 54% a mood disorder, only 13%
403 developed a BSD and 3% BD-1¹³.

404 Our risk calculator focusing on specific symptoms that confer increased BSD risk might lead to
405 new interventions that could target preventing first hypomanic or manic episodes. Attempts to
406 intervene at earlier stages of BD have led to initial positive outcomes⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ and a recent systematic
407 review of trials for participants at high risk of developing BD found preliminary support for the
408 efficacy of aripiprazole in reducing mood symptoms, while psychological interventions were
409 effective for various outcomes⁴⁸. Physical exercise has also been suggested to improve
410 symptoms (e.g. sleep) and psychological functioning in adolescents⁴⁹. Additional research is
411 required before clinical recommendations can be made. It may be that some of these

412 interventions are better suited for some at-risk groups. In any case, close monitoring is
413 recommended for at-risk groups and, when needed, provide early interventions (e.g. for those
414 who develop BD).

415 Our risk calculator has the potential to be integrated into clinical practice as a decision-support
416 tool to enhance the early identification of adolescents at risk of developing BSD (i.e. identifying
417 those at higher risk). Externally validating our prediction model in larger, multi-site cohorts will
418 be essential to refine the model and ensure its robustness across different healthcare settings²³,
419 ⁵⁰. Ultimately, this tool could contribute to precision psychiatry approaches, enabling earlier,
420 preventive interventions that may mitigate the progression to full-threshold BSD and improve
421 long-term outcomes in adolescents at risk⁵¹.

422 Several limitations of this study should be considered. First, half of the participants lacked
423 follow-up data. The baseline comparison of study participants with vs. without post-baseline
424 follow-up did not show differences. However, this result does not fully exclude the possibility of
425 differential attrition of families and patients at higher risk for BSD or those with greater clinical
426 severity, fluctuating symptomatology, or lower engagement with follow-up assessments, which
427 could introduce selection bias, limit generalizability, and potentially underestimate or
428 overestimate the observed frequency of BSD development. Second, given the small sample size
429 with few developments of BSD, power to detect statistically significant group differences for
430 association with BSD risk may have been limited, and the results and their interpretation should
431 be taken cautiously. Larger and longer studies following individuals at risk for BD are
432 recommended. Nevertheless, we did find differences pointing to subsyndromal mania-like
433 symptom presence and severity as clinical markers of future BSD risk, which is consistent with
434 familial high-risk and database study results⁵². We also carried out machine learning analyses
435 to estimate the risk of developing BSD from a set of baseline characteristics. Third, while the K-
436 SADS is the gold standard to diagnose children and adolescents, some symptom collections are

437 based on retrospective data, which may be sensitive to recall bias. However, we tried mitigating
438 against this by interviewing caregivers as well as patients and using the higher rating of the two
439 in case of inconsistency under the assumption that symptoms are not fabricated by rather not
440 noticed (internalizing symptoms by caregivers, externalizing symptoms by patients), forgotten
441 or hidden. Fourth, we included psychiatrically hospitalized adolescents. Hence, generalizability
442 of the model to outpatients requires testing. Moreover, participants were specifically asked
443 about symptoms rather than relying on spontaneous reporting, increasing validity and
444 completeness of the data. Fifth, and related to this methodology, we did not include family
445 history in our risk calculator. While family history has been described as an important predictor
446 of BSD, the deliberate clinical risk enrichment of our sample (not previously studied) was related
447 to psychiatric hospitalization during adolescence and not family history. Future studies including
448 participants with both risk factors are recommended, as they may have a higher associated
449 predictive model performance. Sixth, we did not adjust univariate group differences in the
450 sample characteristics, which were used for descriptive purposes only, for multiple testing. Of
451 the 105 participants with prospective data, 18 developed BSD, including 9 with BD-NOS, 1 BD-II,
452 and 8 BD-I (5 without and 3 with psychotic features). All BSD developments occurred after
453 hospital discharge, i.e., reported mood symptoms at baseline were not contiguous with the
454 development of BSD. Finally, other measured and unmeasured variables may have affected our
455 results. For instance, some patients received psychotropic medications during follow-up or at
456 the time of the assessment, which may have influenced outcomes.

457 In conclusion, we observed prospectively that around 17% adolescents hospitalized for
458 psychiatric problems developed BSD at follow-up. Taking into account the baseline parameters
459 associated with BSD development, such as prevalence of inflated self-esteem/grandiosity and
460 racing thoughts, and severity of talkativeness, increased energy and mood lability the estimated
461 a BSD risk was 22% at 2 years and 36% at 4 years. Our risk estimation calculator, including
462 baseline presence and severity of mania-like symptoms (inflated self-esteem/grandiosity, racing

463 thoughts, overtalkativeness, and increased energy) estimated risk of BSD development. These
464 findings are hoped to inform preventive efforts with the potential to improve outcomes in
465 adolescents at risk for and with emerging BSD. To translate these findings into clinical practice,
466 future research should focus on piloting the risk calculator in real-world settings to evaluate its
467 feasibility and clinical utility. Additionally, prospective external validation studies and clinical
468 trials are needed to refine the model, address limitations, and determine its effectiveness in
469 guiding early intervention strategies.

470

471 **Other information:** Supplementary material has been included to give readers additional
472 information about their work:

473 **-Supplementary eTable 1 – STROBE Statement—Checklist of items in cohort studies**

474 **-Supplementary eTable 2 – The TRIPOD+AI checklist**

475 **-Supplementary eTable 3 – The TRIPOD+AI Abstract checklist**

476 **-Supplementary eTable 4 – Comparison completers versus not completers**

477 **-Supplementary eTable 5 – Prevalence of BPSS-FP Mania Symptom Index, Depression**
478 **Symptom Index and General Symptom Index items at baseline rated as moderated or higher**
479 **severity and association with BSD development**

480 **-Supplementary eFigure 1 – Kaplan-Meier Transition Figures**

481 **-Supplementary eFigure 2 – Operating characteristic curves for predictions of BSD onset within**
482 **the first 17-23 months**

483 **-Supplementary eText 1 - Bipolar Spectrum Disorders characterizations**

484 **-Supplementary eText 2 - Bipolar Prodrome Symptom Interview and Scale-Prospective (BPSS-**
485 **P) details**

486 -Supplementary eCode 1 – Simulations of accuracy estimation using k-fold cross-validation,
487 leave-one-out cross-validation, bootstrap out-of-bag validation, and new dataset validation.

Figure 1. Flow diagram participants in the study

Figure 2A/ Kaplan-Meier Survival Analysis Curve of the Transition Risk to Bipolar-Spectrum Disorders

The number of patients at risk (“N at risk”) represents the number of patients still in the follow-up at each given time point (i.e., that have neither developed a BSD nor been lost to follow-up).

B/ Kaplan-Meier Survival Analysis stratified by high vs. low risk groups according to the Bipolar Spectrum Disorders (BSD) risk calculator

The red line shows the percentage of transitions to BSD in patients estimated to be at high risk by the BSD calculator, while the black line shows the percentage in patients estimated to be at low risk.

Figure 3: Area Under the Curve (AUC) for predictions of the Bipolar Spectrum Disorders (BSD) risk calculator over time (i.e., BSD onsets occurring since the start of the follow-up to each given month).

The central dashed line represents the area under the receiver operating characteristic (AUC), and the shaded region represents its 95% confidence interval at different follow-up times. Months with an AUC statistically higher than 0.5 are represented with a thick red line. AUCs in the first months should be taken

cautiously due to the small number of early developments of BSD. Months 17-18 had only borderline significance (95%CI 0.5-1) in the bootstrap out-of-bag validation and are represented with a thin red line.

Table 1. Characteristics of the sample

Variable	Sample (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
Age (years) mean±SD	15.4±1.3	15.3±1.3	15.5±1.4	0.91	0.562
Sex: % males (N, %)	29 (27.6%)	7 (38.9%)	22 (25.3%)	0.57	0.247
Race (N, %)				1.08	0.711
White	54 (54.5%)	10 (55.6%)	44 (54.3%)		
Black or African American	20 (20.2%)	4 (22.2%)	16 (19.8%)		
Mixed Race	15 (15.2%)	3 (16.7%)	12 (14.8%)		
Asian or Pacific Islander	9 (9.1%)	1 (5.6%)	8 (9.9%)		
Other	1 (1.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.0%)		

Variable	Sample (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
Psychopathology scores mean±SD					
MADRS total	26.5±15.1	28.8±11.8	26.0±15.7	1.01	0.527
CGI-S	4.2±1.0	4.6±1.1	4.2±1.0	1.46	0.123
GAF current	28.3±15.7	29.3±16.2	28.1±15.7	1.00	0.833
GAF high	56.6±14.1	54.8±16.7	56.9±13.6	0.99	0.466
GAF low	23.9±14.7	24.1±16.5	23.8±14.5	1.00	0.861
YMRS total	11.9±10.5	16.1±13.0	11.0±9.7	1.08	0.009
Psychiatric diagnoses					
Number of diagnoses (mean ±SD)	3.2±1.8	3.33±1.9	3.14±1.8	1.09	0.501
Depressive disorders	86 (81.9%)	14 (77.8%)	72 (82.8%)	0.74	0.601

Variable	Sample (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
Major depressive disorder single episode	42 (40%)	7 (38.9%)	35 (40.2%)	1.19	0.721
Major depressive disorder recurrent	20 (19.0%)	3 (16.7%)	17 (19.5%)	0.78	0.699
Major depressive disorder with psychotic features	12 (11.4%)	3 (16.7%)	9 (10.3%)	1.50	0.522
Other unspecified depressive disorder	22 (21.0%)	2 (11.1%)	20 (23.0%)	0.33	0.147
Persistent depressive disorder	12 (11.4%)	4 (22.2%)	8 (9.2%)	4.00	0.018
Trauma- and stressor-related disorders	15 (14.3%)	3 (16.7%)	12 (13.8%)	1.30	0.675
PTSD	8 (7.6%)	2 (11.1%)	6 (6.9%)	2.87	0.168
Adjustment disorder	7 (6.7%)	1 (5.6%)	6 (6.9%)	0.59	0.610
Personality disorder traits	19 (18.1%)	3 (16.7%)	16 (18.4%)	0.99	0.990

Variable	Sample (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
Borderline personality disorder traits	18 (17.1%)	3 (16.7%)	15 (17.2%)	1.03	0.963
Other personality disorder traits	3 (2.9%)	0 (0%)	3 (3.4%)	N.a.	N.a.
Anxiety disorders	47 (44.8%)	7 (38.9%)	40 (46.0%)	0.77	0.597
Generalized anxiety disorder	18 (17.1%)	3 (16.7%)	15 (17.2%)	1.04	0.955
Obsessive compulsive disorder and related	7 (6.7%)	2 (11.1%)	5 (5.7%)	1.38	0.688
Panic disorder	24 (22.9%)	5 (27.8%)	19 (21.8%)	1.71	0.314
Social phobia	8 (7.6%)	1 (5.6%)	7 (8.0%)	0.63	0.654
Other anxiety disorders	16 (15.2%)	0 (0%)	16 (18.4%)	0.00	0.997
Disruptive behavior disorders	43 (41.0%)	10 (55.6%)	33 (37.9%)	1.98	0.152

Variable	Sample (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder	31 (29.5%)	8 (44.4%)	23 (26.4%)	2.35	0.075
Conduct disorder	4 (3.8%)	1 (5.6%)	3 (3.4%)	2.94	0.299
Oppositional defiant disorder	18 (17.1%)	2 (11.1%)	16 (18.4%)	0.49	0.348
Disruptive behavior disorder NOS	7 (6.7%)	3 (16.7%)	4 (4.6%)	2.95	0.090
Substance use disorders	13 (12.4%)	1 (5.6%)	12 (13.8%)	0.56	0.577
Alcohol use disorder	5 (4.8%)	1 (5.6%)	4 (4.6%)	1.54	0.676
Cannabis use disorder	13 (12.4%)	1 (5.6%)	12 (13.8%)	0.56	0.577
Eating disorders	7 (6.7%)	0 (0%)	7 (8.0%)	0.00	0.998
Gender identity disorder	2 (1.9%)	0 (0%)	2 (2.3%)	0.00	0.998
Enuresis	3 (2.9%)	1 (5.6%)	2 (2.3%)	3.46	0.231

Variable	Sample (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
Attenuated Psychosis Syndrome	27 (25.7%)	7 (38.9%)	20 (23.0%)	2.20	0.103
Basic Symptoms (COGDIS)	7 (6.7%)	2 (11.1%)	5 (5.7%)	1.37	0.677
Tic disorders	4 (3.8%)	2 (11.1%)	2 (2.3%)	3.70	0.084
Pharmacological treatment, (N, %)					
Number of treatments (mean \pm SD)	2.7 \pm 1.7	3.2 \pm 1.7	2.6 \pm 1.7	1.2	0.118
Any treatment (N, %)	102 (97.1%)	18 (100.0%)	84 (96.6%)	N.a	N.a.
Antipsychotics	65 (61.9%)	13 (72.2%)	52 (59.8%)	1.71	0.307
Antidepressants	63 (60.0%)	8 (44.4%)	55 (63.2%)	0.44	0.085
Mood stabilizers	38 (36.2%)	11 (61.1%)	27 (31.0%)	3.88	0.006
Mood stabilizers: Lithium	30 (28.6%)	8 (44.4%)	22 (25.3%)	2.83	0.030

Variable	Sample (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
Mood stabilizers: Other (valproate, topiramate, lamotrigine)	13 (12.4%)	4 (22.2%)	9 (10.3%)	2.23	0.162
Anxiolytics	24 (22.9%)	4 (22.2%)	20 (23.0%)	0.92	0.891
Anxiolytics: Benzodiazepines	21 (20.0%)	3 (16.7%)	18 (20.7%)	0.81	0.735
Anxiolytics: Antihistamines and others	6 (5.7%)	1 (5.6%)	5 (5.7%)	0.99	0.994
ADHD medications	13 (12.4%)	5 (27.8%)	8 (9.2%)	3.33	0.023
Other medications	9 (8.6%)	1 (5.6%)	8 (9.2%)	0.46	0.459

Table 2 Severity of BPSS-FP Mania Symptom Index, Depression Symptom Index and General Symptom Index items at baseline and association with BSD development

BPSS-P items (M=mania; D=depression; G=general Symptom Index) mean±SD	Total (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
M1: Mood elevation	1.5±1.7	2.6±1.6	1.3±1.6	1.67	<0.001
M2: Irritability	3.8±1.4	4.4±1.4	3.7±1.5	1.42	0.065
M3: Inflated self-esteem/grandiosity	0.7±1.2	1.4±1.9	0.5±0.9	2.07	<0.001
M4: Decreased need for sleep	0.7±1.5	1.5±2.2	0.5±1.3	1.43	<0.001
M5: Overtalkativeness	1.6±1.9	2.9±2.2	1.3±1.7	1.57	<0.001
M6: Racing thoughts	1.6±2.0	3.3±2.2	1.3±1.7	1.58	<0.001
M7: Distractibility	3.0±2.0	3.8±2.1	2.9±2.0	1.27	0.056
M8: Increased energy	0.9±1.3	1.9±1.6	0.7±1.1	1.60	<0.001
M9: Increased psychomotor activity	3.8±1.7	3.6±1.9	3.9±1.9	1.12	0.389
M10: Reckless or dangerous behavior	3.2±1.9	4.2±1.4	3.0±2.0	1.19	0.133
D1: Depressed mood	4.8±1.4	4.7±1.3	4.8±1.4	0.96	0.796
D2: Anhedonia	3.9±1.8	3.9±1.8	3.9±1.8	1.01	0.926
D3: Decreased appetite	1.7±2.1	1.4±1.9	1.8±2.1	0.89	0.348

BPSS-P items (M=mania; D=depression; G=general Symptom Index) mean±SD	Total (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
D4: Increased appetite	1.7±2.1	2.1±2.3	1.7±2.1	1.06	0.598
D5: Insomnia	3.1±2.1	3.5±2.1	3.0±2.1	1.16	0.211
D6: Hypersomnia	1.7±2.1	1.9±2.1	1.7±2.1	1.11	0.351
D7: Decreased psychomotor activity	2.0±2.0	2.4±1.9	2.0±2.0	1.13	0.322
D8: Decreased energy	3.5±2.0	3.9±1.3	3.4±2.1	1.15	0.268
D9: Worthlessness/guilt	3.8±1.9	3.6±1.9	3.9±1.9	0.97	0.807
D10: Decreased concentration	3.2±2.0	4.2±1.4	3.0±2.0	1.47	0.014
D11: Indecision	1.8±1.7	2.3±1.8	1.7±1.7	1.2	0.146
D12: Suicidality	4.3±2.2	3.9±2.4	4.4±2.2	0.88	0.224
G1: Mood lability	3.2±2.1	4.4±1.8	3.0±2.1	1.57	<0.001
G2: Oppositionality	2.5±1.9	2.9±2.0	2.4±1.9	1.22	0.141
G3: Anger/aggressiveness	3.2±1.9	3.8±1.8	3.1±1.9	1.38	0.034
G4: Anxiety	3.6±2.0	3.6±2.1	3.7±2.0	1.0	0.993
G5: Self-injurious behavior	2.8±2.4	2.3±2.6	2.9±2.3	0.89	0.259
G6: Obsessions	1.0±1.6	1.3±1.6	1.0±1.6	1.09	0.491

BPSS-P items (M=mania; D=depression; G=general Symptom Index) mean±SD	Total (n=105)	BSD during follow up (n=18)	No BSD during follow up (n=87)	HR BSD development	P-value
G7: Positive psychotic symptoms	1.4±2.0	2.0±2.4	1.3±1.94	1.27	0.021
G8: Negative psychotic symptoms	0.9±1.5	1.3±1.8	0.8±1.4	1.21	0.182
G9: Disorganized psychotic symptoms	0.4±0.9	0.3±0.7	0.4±0.9	1.09	0.786

BPSS-FP: Bipolar Prodrome Symptom Interview and Scale-Full, Prospective. Severity is rated on an ordinal scale with 0=absent, 1=questionably present, 2=mild, 3=moderate, 4=moderately severe, 5=severe, 6=extreme.

Table 3 Model: predictors selected and individual performance

	Individual performance		Model	
	HR	95% CI	beta	Relevance
Prevalence of M3 - Inflated self-esteem/grandiosity	11.3	(4.05-31.3)	0.833	68.1%
Prevalence of M6 - Racing thoughts	6.21	(2.19-17.6)	0.079	5.3%
Severity of M5 – Overtalkativeness	1.57	(1.24-1.98)	0.030	7.6%
Severity of M8 - Increased energy	1.60	(1.25-2.04)	0.035	8.2%

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